

Evolution of iron toxicity symptoms in stressed and control fields and coefficients of variation at different stages of assessment. Data pooled for 28 genotypes and 3 replications.

The *sativa* varieties ranged between 124 and 142 d to maturity (mean of 130), and average iron toxicity across varieties increased to a maximum of 4.8 at 75 DAT, with a range of 2.0-7.0 (1 = no symptoms; 9 = dead plants). Eleven entries showed maximal symptoms at 60 DAT, 24 at 75 DAT, and 15 at 90 DAT. Those with marginal symptoms at these sampling dates included the two *O. glaberrima* land races, which attained their maximum score at 45 DAT. The lowest coefficient of variation of 20.08% for iron toxicity scores across genotypes was also observed at 75 DAT (see figure).

Iron toxicity caused significant reductions ($P < 0.001$) in agronomic parameters as compared with the control plot, but the scores were significantly

Correlation between three ways of assessing rice varieties for tolerance for iron toxicity and some agronomic parameters.

Parameter	Score at 75 DAT ^a	Maximum score	Cumulative score
% height reduction	0.63**	0.61**	0.69**
% yield reduction	0.60**	0.64**	0.74**
% panicle reduction	0.46*	0.47*	0.54**
% tiller reduction	-0.003 ns	-0.015 ns	0.021 ns
% spikelet reduction	0.11 ns	0.13 ns	0.24 ns

^a DAT = days after transplanting.

correlated with reductions in yield ($r = 0.63^{**}$) and plant height ($r = 0.59^{**}$). No such relation was noted with reduction in tiller number ($r = -0.003$ ns).

The cumulative score may be the best parameter to assess varieties, as it showed the highest correlations with agronomic performance, especially yield (see table). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Yumehatamochi, a new upland rice variety in Japan

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In 1996 in Japan, upland rice was grown on 13,000 ha, or 0.7% of the total rice cultivated area, and comprised only 0.3% of the total rice produced. A new upland rice variety Yumehatamochi has been released into Ibaraki, Toichigi, and Gunna prefectures, which had about 60% of the total Japanese upland rice area in 1996. Yumehatamochi means "dreamy (excellent) glutinous upland rice" in Japanese. It is derived from the cross Norinmochi 4 / / Norinmochi 4/JC81/ / Norinmochi 4. The traditional Indian variety JC81 was chosen as parent because of its deep root system. Norinmochi 4 is a Japanese upland rice variety with high resistance to blast. Yumehatamochi is a medium-maturing variety with medium culm length (Table 1). This variety inherited abundant rooting in deeper soil layers from its parent, JC81.

Root tips of Yumehatamochi reached to a soil layer of 85 cm depth, which was about 20 cm deeper than those of other varieties. Therefore, Yumehatamochi

Table 1. Characteristics of Yumehatamochi and popular local variety Tsukubahatamochi. Ibaraki, Japan.

Character	Yumehatamochi	Tsukubahatamochi
Duration (d)	124	121
Culm length (cm)	71	78
Panicle length (cm)	19.8	20.5
Panicle number (no. m ²)	316	297
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.42	3.09
1,000-grain wt (g)	21.9	20.4
Grain quality ^a	5.2	5.0
Eating quality ^b	1.0	4.0

^aAv from 1989 to 1995. ^b1 = excellent, 9 = poor,

mochi showed outstanding yields in the drought years of 1992 and 1994 (Table 2). The drought resistance of this variety is the highest of other released upland rice varieties in Japan.

In general, glutinous rice is used to make rice cake. The eating quality of rice cake from upland rice has been inferior to that of lowland rice varieties. Only lowland varieties have been used to make rice cake. According to eating quality studies performed in our institute, however, rice cake made from Yumehatamochi showed high smoothness and softness and it was similar to rice cake made from lowland rice varieties. Eating quality of Yumehatamochi was shown as the best among Japanese upland rice varieties. ■

Table 2. Yield and grain quality of Yumehatamochi and Tsukubahatamochi in drought years. Ibaraki, Japan.

Variety	Total test years ^a			Drought years ^b		
	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Rate (%)	Grain quality ^c	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Rate (%)	Grain quality ^c
Yumehatamochi	3.42	111	5.2	1.64	148	5.2
Tsukubahatamochi	3.09	100	5.0	1.11	100	5.9

^a From 1989 to 1995. ^b 1992 and 1994. ^c 1=excellent, 10=poor.